

On a Conjecture of F. Smarandache

Wang Yang^{1,2} Zhang Hong Li^{1,3}

(1. Department of Mathematics, Northwest University; 2. Department of Mathematics, Nanyang Teacher's College, Henan China 473061; 3. Xi'an Finance and Accounting School, Xi'an Shanxi China 710048)

Abstract: The main purpose of this paper is to solve a problem generated by Professor F.Smarandache.

Key word: Permutation sequence; k-power.

Let n be a positive integer, n is called a k -power if $n=m^k$, where k and m are positive integer, and $k \geq 2$. Obviously, if n is a k -power, p is a prime, then we have $p^k | n$, if $p | n$.

In his book "Only Problems, not Solutions", Professor F.Smarandache defined a permutation sequence: 12, 1342, 135642, 13578642, 13579108642, 135791112108642, 1357911131412108642, 13579111315161412108642, 135791113151718161412108642, ..., and generated a conjecture: there is no any k -power among these numbers. The main purpose of this paper is to prove that this conjecture is true.

Suppose there is a k -power $a(n)$ among the permutation sequence. Noting the fact: $12=2^2 \times 3$, we may immediately get: $a(n) \geq 1342 > 10000$. For the last two digits of $a(n)$ is 42, so we have $a(n) \equiv 42 \pmod{100}$

Noting that $4 | 100$, we may immediately deduce : $a(n) \equiv 42 \equiv 2 \pmod{4}$.

So we get $2 | a(n)$, $4 \nmid a(n)$. However, 2 is a prime, then $4 | a(n)$ contradicts with $4 \nmid a(n)$. So $a(n)$ is not a k -power.

This complete the proof of the conjecture.

REFERENCES

- [1] Chengdong Pang, Chengbiao Pang. Elementary Number Theory. 6th ed. Beijing, 1992.
- [2] F.Smarandache. Only problems, not Solutions [M]. Xiquan publishing House, 1993:25.